

ISSUES OF INVOLVEMENT OF WOMEN IN SOCIO-CULTURAL LIFE IN THE 20-30S OF THE XX CENTURY. (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE SOUTHERN PROVINCES)

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Annotation. This article highlights the work done by the Soviet government in the 20-30s of the XX century in order to increase the social activity of women in the southern regions of Uzbekistan. During the implementation of this issue, the cultural and educational institutions established for women, their types, and their work were shown.

Key words: cultural and educational institution, mobile yurts, red tea rooms, red corners, women's clubs, the Khujum movement, socialist competition, reading room, volost, county, party committee, collective farm, state farm.

The Soviet authorities developed a way to implement the event of a "cultural revolution" among the population, starting from the second half of the 20s of the 20th century, in order to further strengthen its political and economic position. Especially this situation has become serious in socio-cultural life, which is considered important in changing the minds of people. Political emphasis was placed on the issue of women in this framework, giving the implementation of the events of the "Cultural Revolution". In particular, the issue of women is one of the most serious socio-political issues in all countries of the world. As noted above, during the years of Soviet power, the participation of women in socio-cultural life was subordinated to political goals.

In 1920-1924, the southern regions of Uzbekistan were part of the BXSU, and another of the important social problems that should be noted during this period was the issue of women, which made up more than half of the members of the society. In the above Years, special attention was paid to the issue of women. The government of the Republic of Bukhara has developed measures to increase the rights and role of women in the development of society, while actively involving them in social and cultural life. That is, a law was passed not to marry girls under the age of 18. In order to bring women to life more broadly, Bukhara hosted the Khotun day festival for the first time on March 17, 1922[1:25]. The details of this holiday with the participation of women are widely covered in the article "day of khotun in Bukhara", published in the newspaper "Bukhara akhbori". There was also a large-scale propaganda effort

aimed at attracting women to social life and ensuring their participation in the processes of production.

On March 24, 1924, the plenum of the Central Asian Bureau of the CCP(b) considered this issue and set measures to hold a meeting of women in places, to employ them, to establish women's Soviets in the regional districts. [2: 31] the process of implementing these measures was carried out under sharp, fierce ideological and class struggles. By the middle of the 20s of the 20th century, a system of cultural and educational institutions was created in Uzbekistan, which was intended to serve the Soviet state, its ideology, including in its southern regions.

At a meeting of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan on February 12, 1925, the resolution "on women's affairs" was adopted. [3: 11] this resolution addressed the issue of establishing the activities of separate cultural and educational institutions for women in the southern regions of the Republic, including unung. According to the decision of the meeting, special attention was paid to the issue of attracting women to spiritual and educational spheres in order to realize their rights. The work that should be carried out to ensure the active participation of women in social life has been outlined. Special portable fireplaces for women, Red Tea Rooms, red corners, women's clubs were organized. First of all, the issue of increasing the social activity of women was put before these institutions. Throughout the country, club institutions for women began to be established. The first of the women's clubs in the Republic opened in Tashkent in 1924.[4: 227] in the following years, such institutions were also established in other cities of Uzbekistan. By 1925, the first women's club was also established in Qarshi. The club was headed by Muqaddam Zokirova.[5: 39] by 1926, women's clubs were also working in the Qarshi, Shahrisabz, Ghuzar districts of the Kashkadarya region. Work by club members to attract local women to the clubs was done with difficulty. In its early years, clubs operated at the disposal of public education. By 1926-1927, the membership of the women's club Krupskaya in Qarshi was 250. Of these, only 56 were Indigenous women. All cultural and educational institutions-in particular, women's clubs-also operated on the idea of denying cultural heritage against National Culture, National Customs and religious values.

By 1927, women's clubs were also established in Termez, Denov, Sariosiya and Sherabad districts of Surkhandarya region.[6:68] Rozikhol Elmurodova, Fatima Aliyeva, Tursunoy Rizakulova, Zulfiya Ziyoyeva, Gurbanoy Hakimova headed the women's clubs. In the early years, the main members of the clubs

were considered urban women. Ways were developed to attract local women to clubs. In particular, consultancies were established for their children. For themselves, the activities of schools for the termination of illiteracy, cabinets advising on legal issues were established.[7: 3] active women went door-to-door and carried out propaganda work among women. The next case was the employment of women visiting clubs. To do this, artels were formed, which were associated with quilting, confectionery sehs, carpet weaving and several other crafts. In these years, the activities of women's corners were also established. On the established red corners, the activities of the library and recitals were established. It introduced regular voice-over readings of books, newspapers and magazines. All of the red corners established in the southern regions of Uzbekistan functioned for women.

In 1927-1928, the number of red corners established for women in the Kashkadarya region was 4, while in 1929-30 the number reached 11. Of these, 8 operated in villages. In 1927-28, the Surkhandarya region operated 6 women's red corners, while in 1929-30 the number was 15.[8: 81] Red corners became one of the main forms of Organization of mass-political work among women. Even in the following years, special attention was paid to this type of cultural and educational institutions and their number increased. In 1937, red corners were established in almost all districts of the province, bringing the number to 107.

So, the work of the Soviet authorities on the involvement of women in social work paid off. Of course, the contribution of cultural and educational institutions was great in this process. It seems that the activities of these institutions in the 20-30 years of the XX century were transformed into an institution for political affairs.

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